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ASSESSMENT OF PMTCT SERVICE QUALITY AT BEDDELLE AND METTU KARL HOSPITALS, IN ILU ABABORA ZONE OROMIYA REGION, SOUTH WEST ETHIOPIA.2015

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ABSTRACT

Background: - Globally, there are an estimated 34 million people living with HIV (PLHIV), the vast majority of who live in sub-Saharan Africa and every day over 5700 persons die from AIDS. Mother-to-Child Transmission is by far the largest source of Human immunodeficiency virus infection in children under the age of 15 years and the virus can be transmitted during pregnancy, labor, delivery, or after child's birth during breast feeding. PMTCT service consumption at Antenatal care was not assessed in the hospitals. So the objective was to assess the quality of PMTCT service. **Methods:** - The study was conducted at Bedelle and Mettu Karl hospitals with a hospital based cross sectional study design. The study conducted from March – April 30/2015. About 195 pregnant women were participated in exit interview and 6 direct observations were done. Data on client satisfaction, counselors' communicative skills, duration and content of pre- and post-test counseling was collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from UNAIDS tools. **Result:** - One hundred sixty-six 166 (85.1%) of the clients said that the counseling room's door was closed, and 131(67.2%) of the clients were need to have different counselors. The mean duration of pretest counseling sessions was 20.8 minutes. Both the hospitals were observed offering individual pre- and post-test counseling by trained health personnel. **Conclusion:** - Overall, counselor's communicative skill (introductory/interpersonal relationship, gathering information from the clients, and giving information to the clients) was generally "satisfactory". The majority of pre-test sessions included the basic information on HIV transmission and prevention and PMTCT. However, this study revealed that the discussions were rudimentary and lacking in depth and coverage in many of the counseling sessions. The administrative health bureau should facilitate ongoing (refreshment) training for the counselors to equip them with recent information. As well additional health workers should be trained to share the burden of the work.

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INTRODUCTION

Background

Globally, there are an estimated 34 million people living with HIV (PLHIV), the vast majority of who live in sub-Saharan Africa, and every day over 5700 persons die from AIDS because of inadequate access to HIV prevention and treatment services (1). Mother-to-Child Transmission (MTCT) is by far the largest source of HIV infection in children under the age of 15yrs and the virus can be transmitted during pregnancy, labor, delivery, or after child's birth during breast feeding. Vertical transmission of HIV mostly occurs during labor and delivery and in a population which has traditional practice of breast feeding, it accounts for more than one third of all cases of MTCT (2).

Sub-Sahara African countries are more heavily affected by HIV/AIDS than any other region of the world. An estimated 22.4 million people are living with HIV in the Sub-Sahara region about two thirds of the global total. In 2008 around 1.4 million people died from AIDS in sub-Sahara Africa and 1.9 million people become infected with HIV since the beginning of the epidemic and more than 14 million children have lost one or both parents to AIDS(3).

In Ethiopia HIV prevalence rate in 2010 is estimated to be 2.4%. Currently there are more than 1.2 million (45% male and 55% female) PLWHA and 75,420 HIV positive pregnant women are anticipated in Ethiopia (4). The estimated number of new adult AIDS cases was 137,949. The number of new HIV infection was 128,922 (353 per day) including 30,338 HIV positive births (5). There were 134,450 (368 per day) AIDS related deaths including 20,929 children under 14 years (83.6% under age five).The number of AIDS orphans age less than 17 reached 744,757.The number of PLWHA, in need of antiretroviral treatment (ART) was 277,757 including 43,055 (15.5%) children aged less than 14 years.(4,5).

Oromia National Regional State being one of the most populous regions in the country is one of the highly exposed regions. According to the single point HIV prevalence estimate, the HIV prevalence in Oromia is estimated at 1.5% (1.8% female and 1.2 male) in 2009. The HIV prevalence among the urban populations estimated at 6.1% (7.3%in female and 4.9% in males).The corresponding estimate among rural population was 0.6%(0.7% in female and 0.5% in male)(6).Reports of one month in the MKRH show that 98(ninety-eight) pregnant women have tested for HIV and 1(one) is positive to HIV and 198(one hundred eight) delivery service was given and 3(three) was positive.

The Government of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia is committed to reducing the spread of HIV/AIDS and addresses the consequences of the epidemic in the population. The national HIV/AIDS policy was enacted in 1998; and in 2001, the National HIV/AIDS Council declared HIV a national emergency. The National HIV/AIDS strategic framework calls for a multi-sectoral response, guaranteeing rights of all people living with HIV/AIDS, and facilitating the supply and use of antiretroviral drugs. Ethiopia has adopted the WHO/UNICEF/UNAIDS 4-pronged PMTCT strategy as a key entry point to HIV care for women, men and families. Technical interventions, including antiretroviral medications, essential obstetric care, health system management and resource allocation, and gender bias are part of the national comprehensive PMTCT program. Addressing all four prongs has potential to interrupt the cycle that leads to MTCT at several points (4).

Statement of the problem

At the end of 2009, an estimated 2.5 million children were living with HIV, over 90% of them infected through mother-to-child transmission (MTCT). Without treatment, about half of these infected children will die before their second year birthday. Without intervention, the risk of MTCT ranges from 20% to 45%. With specific interventions in non-breastfeeding populations, the risk of MTCT can be reduced to less than 2% and to 5% or less in breastfeeding populations (2, 3). In Ethiopia, there are an estimated 90,311 pregnancies among women living with HIV/AIDS, resulting in 14,276 HIV-positive births. More than 120,000 children under age 14 years are thought to be living with HIV/AIDS and 754,000 children have been orphaned due to the epidemic (5).

Oromia is one of the severely affected regions by HIV/AIDS pandemic. The regional HIV positive pregnant women are 23,940 and the annual HIV-Positive births are 3861 (6). Access to HIV test as early as possible during pregnancy enables pregnant women living with HIV to benefit from the necessary interventions to reduce the risk of transmitting HIV to their children (4). Measuring the quality of HCT in PMTCT programs is very important.

This study, therefore, tries to assess the quality of antenatal linked HIV counseling and testing in terms of available resource, counselors' competence, content of discussion and satisfaction clients on pre- and post-test counseling provided to pregnant women through the program to prevent mother-to-child transmission of HIV in Bedlle and Mettu karl hospital.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Study area and period

The study was facility based cross sectional study applying both qualitative (observation) and quantitative methods in Bedle and Mettu Karl hospitals, from March – April 30/2015. Bedlle and Mettu karl hospitals are the hospitals in I/A/B zone. Mettu karl hospital is located in Mettu town which is the zonal town. The zone is bordered by SNNPR in South and Southeast, Gambella southwest, Wollega in the west and Jimma in the north. According to the 2005.E.C censuses, the number of inhabitant was estimated to 53,792 (22,857 males and 31,935 females). Majority of the inhabitants of Mettu town and bedlle twon belong to the Oromo ethnic group. Generally, agriculture, government employee and small scale trading are means by which the local people earn their living.

2.2 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling was used to take the two PMTCT providing hospitals in the district for exit interview. The hospitals have served for a long time. For exit interview, sample size (n) was determined based on single population proportion formula with 95% CI and 5% marge of error.

All pregnant women in the study period were employed for the study until the calculated sample size was obtained. The average pregnant women that visit the hospitals were estimated to be 300 women. From these populations 195 of them were included in the study.

Study Variables

Dependent variables

Quality of PMTCT service

Independent variables

Age

Marital status

Occupation

Educational Status

Availability of resource

Data collection technique

Quantitative and qualitative data collection methods were implemented. Two BSc health professionals trained on PMTCT were recruited for supervision and ten BSc health professionals were assigned for data collection at ANC and delivery room from this two of them were performed direct observation. The instruments were adapted from tools for HIV voluntary counseling and testing March 2000 UNAIDS (29) and Baseline assessment tools for preventing mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT) of HIV (30). Exit interview was translated to Afan Oromo and retranslated to English by different persons and compared with the original one to maintain the consistency. All data collectors and supervisors who can speak Afan Oromo were recruited from other place of study hospitals to minimize the information bias.

Counselor-client interaction observations

All available counselors at the PMTCT sites was observed using checklist while they were giving counseling service on both pre-test and post-test counseling session using one counseling session every other day to check coverage of basic points of counseling explained in the national guideline 2007(7). The observation was take place depending on the 2000 VCT manuals of WHO which recommends 3-5 observations session per facility (29). Interviewer was explained the objective and the purpose of the study for counselor and client to have consent in the observation sections 2.4.2 *Client exit interview*

Pregnant women who came from April–May 1/2015 were interviewed by PMTCT trained nurses in the hospitals using structured questioners to provide clients with an opportunity of explaining how service delivery conducted and what can be done.

Data processing & analysis

Different data management methods were employed. The quantitative data were checked for completeness, consistency, cleaned and coded before entry. The final data file were brought together and entered to SPSS version 16 for analysis. Recoding and re-categorizing were done for relevant variables as needed. Descriptive statistics such as means and proportions were calculated and findings were presented using frequency tables and graphs. The qualitative data were analyzed manually by summarizing into key thematic area and presented as a narrative summary and used to answer the why quotations that need explanations. Data from different sources were triangulated. In addition, data were used complementarily to assess different aspects of the overall degree of quality implementation. Judgment matrix and the national guideline for PMTCT 2007 were used for the purpose of judging the program's performance. The questionnaires and the soft copy of the data with multiple backups were kept by the principal evaluators.

Ethical Consideration

Letter of ethical clearance was taken from Mettu University, College of Public Health and Medical Sciences Ethical Board to Bedlle and Mettu kal hospitals. During data collection all respondents were informed about the purpose and advantages of the study to the community, asked their permission and informed verbal consent was obtained privately and individually prior to the interview and the information gathered was kept properly. Moreover, data from the study subjects was kept confidential and clients were informed that declining to participate in the study would not affect them from the service

RESULT

Socio Demographic Characteristics

In the exit interview, 195 antenatal care clients from 2 Hospitals were interviewed at exit points. Majority, (50.3%) of them were in the age group of 20-24, followed by age group of 25-29, which accounted for (33.8%) and the rest (3.8%) were in the age group of 35-40. The mean age of the respondents was 23.91 years (the youngest being 17 and the oldest 35). Nearly 68(33.3%) of the respondents were Orthodox Christian religion followed by Muslim (31.4%). Protestants accounted for (30.9%). Majority of the respondents (92.2%) were married. Concerning the educational back ground, about half of mothers (46.2%) were in grades 7-12 (or 10+2), and college or university levels accounted (19.5%). Nearly 1/3 (15.9 %) were in the grade levels of 1-6 and the rest were either illiterate (9.2%) or only able to read/write (9.2%). Occupationally, (42.1%) were housewives, (19.5%) were employed in different private and government agencies, (26.7%) were merchants, and 31(7.4%) were unemployed/jobless. Daily laborers and students accounted for (11.8%).

Table 1:- Socio-demographic characteristics of exit interview in Bedlle and Mettu Karl Hospitals in Ilu Aba Bora Zone, Oromiya region, South West Ethiopia 2015.

Age of the women	15-19	19	9.7
	20-24	98	50.3
	25-29	66	33.8
	30-34	11	0.5
	35-39	1	1.1
	Total	195	100
Educational status	Unable to read and write	18	9.2
	Only read and write	18	9.2
	1-6	31	15.9
	7-12	90	46.2
	>12	38	19.5
	Total	195	100.0
Religious	Muslim	64	32.8
	Orthodox	68	34.9
	Protestant	63	32.3
	Total	195	100
Occupation of the women	No job	82	42.1
	Professional	38	19.5
	Merchant	52	26.7
	others	23	11.8
	Total	195	100
Marital status	Married	3	1.5
	Single	188	96.4
	Separated	4	2.1
	Total	195	100

Clients' Reasons for Coming to the Health Centers

Majority, 82 (42.1%) of the clients specifically came to the health centers to get ANC (antenatal care) follow up services, 50 (25.6%) came for first ANC follow up and only 9 (4.6%) for HIV testing of PMTCT (prevention of mother to child transmission of HIV) services, and the rest 44(22.6%) came for different reasons, among which were for treatment of illnesses, for vaccination, and some were referral cases

Fig. 2. Exit interview for clients' specific reasons of coming to Bedlle and Mettu Karl Hospitals in Ilu Aba Bora Zone, Oromiya region, South West Ethiopia 2015.

Concerning clients' satisfaction with the services, 166 (85.1%) of the clients said that the counseling room's door was closed 131(67.2%) of the clients were need to have different counselors and if they were given an option to see another counselor, 131(67.2%) were strongly agreed on the result. (Table 2).

Table 2:- client exit interview on the condition of counseling room door's preference of different counselors for quality of PMTCT service in Bedlle and Mettu karl Hospitals, In Ilu Ababora Zone, Southwest Ethiopia.2015.

Response		Frequency	Percent
Door closed	Yes	166	85.1
	No	29	14.9
	Total	195	100.0
Different counselor	Yes	131	67.2
	No	64	32.8
	Total	195	100.0

One hundred fifty nine (81.5%) felt comfortable with the information that they got from the counselors'; 104 (53.3%) were very satisfied with technical competence of the counselors.

Table 3:- exit interview result showing PMTCT client response on the satisfaction on the information for decision and technical competence of HIV testing in Bedelle and Mett karl hospitals, In Ilu Aba bora zone, southwest Ethiopia 2015.

Information for decision of HIV testing	Frequency	Percent
yes enough information	159	81.5
the counselor made the decision	14	7.2
not enough information	22	11.3
Total	195	100.0
Technical competence		
very competent	104	53.3
competent	88	41.1
natural	1	0.5
incompetent	2	1
Total		100

Observation of counseling sessions

Four counselors were observed in nine counseling sessions on their job. This method of evaluating the content and quality of counseling sessions was acceptable to all counselors and the counselees. The total number of individual counseling sessions observed was 9 (5 pre- and 4 post-test observations), all of the post-test counseling sessions observed were with HIV negative pregnant women. The mean duration of pretest counseling sessions was 20.8 minutes. Both the hospitals were observed offering individual pre- and post-test counseling by trained health personnel.

Observation for the Contents of Individual Pre-test Counseling

Regarding observation of pre-test counseling sessions, 5 sessions/cases were observed while counseling was in progress (Table 3). Of the 5 pre-test counseling sessions observed, in 3 of the sessions Benefits of testing and test process was discussed; in 9 of the sessions, mothers' capacity to cope up with Discordance and partner HIV testing and Risk reduction was assessed; however, in 2 pre-test Counseling session the counselor did not discuss about risk reduction and PMTCT, support services, and antenatal care that have potential needs and possible supports available for the community. In 3 of the sessions clients were allowed time to think through issues of Exclusive breastfeeding.

Table:-4 check list for the pre-test individual counseling session observation for quality of PMTCT service in Bedle and Mettu karl Hospitals, In Ilu Ababora Zone, Southwest Ethiopia.2015.

Pre-Test Session	Yes	No
Risk reduction	4	1
Testing process	5	0
Discordance and partner test	5	0
PMTCT support	3	2

Observation for the Contents of Individual Post-test Counseling

Four clients who had undergone HIV blood test were observed while given post test individual counseling and all the post-test counseling sessions. Accordingly, in all the 4 post test cases, the test results were given to the clients simply and clearly in a state of neutral tone; and in 1 of the cases, there was no discussion on Partner HIV testing and Disclosure of test result. In 1 of the observation there was no discussion about Antenatal and postnatal care and safe delivery. Although in 2 of the cases there was no Provide referral/take home information, family and social implications of the results. However, in all post-test observation there was discussion about Risk reduction of the cases were counseled to adopt safer sex practices and to be re-tested after 3 months, if there is a recent risk of exposure.

Table 5:- check list for the post-test individual counseling session observation for quality of PMTCT service in Bedlle and Mettu karl Hospitals, In Ilu Ababora Zone, Southwest Ethiopia. 2014/15.

Post-test Counseling:	Yes	No
Provide HIV test result	4	0
Partner HIV testing and Disclosure	2	2
Risk reduction	4	0
Antenatal and postnatal care and safe delivery	3	1
Exclusive breastfeeding	3	1
Infant follow and care	3	1
Provide referral/take home information	2	2

Operational aspect of the PMTCT sites (Interview with counselors)

Regarding interview with counselors working on PMTCT at the time of survey, 3 of the counselors responded to the questionnaire. All the interviewed PMTCT counselors were 2 clinical nurses and 1 midwifery, and all were appointed to become PMTCT counselors by their heads. One of the three PMTCT counselors had taken the basic VCT counseling courses 6 months before the interview, and the remaining 2 had not attended the additional PMTCT training before 2 years. All of them had not taken refreshment training in the past five years. Two of them believed that they need further training.

DISCUSSION

The main objective of PMTCT is to reduce the transmission of HIV infection from HIV infected mothers to children. To achieve this objective the service has to be available to be used by pregnant women

According to the reports of PMTCT coordinators of the Hospitals, both of them are offering pre-test counseling individually and post-test counseling after blood test. The Hospitals had an HCT uptake rate of 100% by ANC attendees. This is in line with the findings of a retrospective study done in Addis Ababa among ANC attendees in ten government health centers from 2008 (38), which stage indicated that overall PMTCT utilization rate was 100% among PMTCT counseled ANC attendees. This may be as a result of an opt-out strategy being carried out throughout the country currently. Availability of separate room for counseling is one of the minimum prerequisites in establishing HCT services. The counseling room should provide audiovisual privacy; conversations between clients and counselors should not be seen or overheard by others (22). However the hospitals are using the ANC room for both service which decrease time wastage.

Both of the hospitals have counselor of nurses and midwifery profession in their backgrounds before they become counselors. This may be an advantage since relatively nurses and midwifery are expected to have better knowledge of health matters than non-health background counselors, and as a result, they would be more confident and skilled/experienced in counseling their clients better. Poor quality counseling can result in misunderstanding and even resistance to behavior change. Counselors need adequate training and ongoing support and supervision to ensure that they give good quality counseling and can cope with their work load (23); but this study indicated that 2 of the 4 counselors had not taken the basic VCT training, 2 of them also never had a refreshment training, and all, but one counselor believed that they would need further refreshment training to be equipped with recent information about HIV and PMTCT. Some PMTCT coordinators also shared the counselors' idea and believed the compromise of the quality of their services as a result of shortage of trained human power and lack of refreshment training for their counselors. This finding may seem to be better than the finding of a study done in 2006 in Addis Ababa which indicated that 83.1% of the general VCT counselors had never been given an ongoing training (24). The lack of training, particularly an ongoing training and technical support of counselors working for the PMTCT program, could lead to be exhausted of counselors or to a decline in the quality of counseling services with time (25).

Observation of the counseling sessions was acceptable to both the counselors and antenatal attendees. The pre-test counseling topics were fairly consistent in both sites and commonly addressed topics included about HIV/AIDS transmission/preventions, MTCT, benefits of testing and discordance and partner HIV testing. However, provided only rudimentary information hastily, which do not enable the clients to make informed decision/consent.

It is an opportunity to provide prevention information, and individual pre-test counseling helps the pregnant women to explore personal HIV risk behaviors and related issues, and concerns as well as for clarification of information (17). Entirely eliminating pre-test counseling or providing insufficient information minimizes the opportunities for ensuring informed consent and potentially makes receiving a positive test result more difficult to deal with (39). The national PMTCT guideline also recommends that the client should be given pre-test information on HIV/AIDS and PMTCT, and that the provider must inform the client that she has the right to say "no" (to opt out) and this decision by no means affects the services she will get from the health facility (4).

The communication skill of the counselors was assessed for introductory/interpersonal relationship, gathering information from the clients, and giving information to the clients. The counselors' communicative skill with clients was "satisfactory" generally. For instance, the counselors greeted the clients and introduced themselves in 3 of the observation sessions all of the cases were attentively listened to. This finding of skill of interpersonal relationship was similar with study done in Thailand in 2000 and lower with study done in South Africa in 2004 (31, 30), in which 56% of the cases were greeted in the former and >95% cases were attentively and supportively listened to in the latter study. The lower results of the current study may be due to the fact that the hospitals had shortage of trained human power as indicated by the PMTCT coordinators.

It is clear that a client will make a good decision and adhere to the information given to prevent MTCT only after the client receives quality counseling and care from a competent counselor with good counseling and interpersonal communication skills (25). Accordingly, during giving information to the clients, in a bit greater than 75% of the sessions, the counselors gave simple and clear information to the clients. However, only in less than a half of the cases main issues discussed during giving information were summarized for pregnant women. These findings are more or less comparable to the finding of a study done in Addis Ababa (31).

As found in a similar study in Addis Ababa the majority of pre-test sessions included the basic information on HIV transmission/prevention and PMTCT. However, in this study the discussions were basic and lacked depth and coverage in many of the counseling sessions. Many of the counselors were making haste. Moreover, a quarter of the clients were not asked to freely consent or dissent HIV testing. This finding is similar to the study done in South Africa (30). This may negatively affect overall ANC utilization by the mothers and an ongoing counseling if the rights of women are violated.

In this study, counseling session observations revealed that more than 66% of the clients were counseled for more than 20 min. The mean duration of pre-test counseling sessions was 20.8 minutes. A mean of 20.8 minutes may seem to higher than national PMTCT Guideline that recommends individual pre-test sessions to last 5-15 minutes (4); however, it is noteworthy that 66% of the clients received a pre-test counseling that lasted for more than 20 minutes.

Generally, this study pointed out that adequate information was passed to clients during the pre-test counseling. However, there was less, another quarter of the clients were not checked whether they had understood the information they were given on MTCT, and only with 6.5% of the cases were potential needs of the women and possible supports in the community explored/assessed. These results, however, are better than that obtained from a similar study done in Thailand (31).

Even though the basic topics were covered in the post-test sessions too, there were significant shortcomings in the comprehensiveness/depth of the information given, coverage of the clients, and in the time allotted for the post test counseling. For instance, discussion of the meaning of the results; personal, family and social implications of the results; and information on safer sex were covered only by 57.1%, 25.7% and 37.1% of the sessions respectively (irrespective of the clients' HIV status), and the duration of post-test counseling was unusually short. Counseling is believed to enable people assess their personal risks for HIV and develop a risk reduction strategy, helps people to adhere to advice and treatment, and contribute to positive living and acceptance of the HIV results or status and is meant to assist clients in disclosing positive HIV status (15, 32). However, the short time spent on this counseling for most of the clients confirms the inadequate facilitation of this important task. This study pointed out that 68.6% of the post-test counseled women received a counseling that lasted less than 5 minutes (mean = 3 min, and 31.4% of the sessions being completed within only 1 minute) as opposed to a similar study done in Thailand (31), that lasted between 5-75 minutes, with a mean of 14 minutes. This finding is, however similar to the study done in Kenya (32) and could be due to the fact that the counselors were overwhelmed with large numbers of clients, and that they ignored the prescribed counseling protocols. It is evident that it is difficult to equip the counselees with the relevant and necessary information in such a short period of counseling.

HCT is a critical component of PMTCT programs and has been a recommended practice in overall HIV/AIDS prevention and care programs, with a high level of scientific evidence. Even though almost all the clients believed that HCT was helpful for the women during pregnancy, Assessing client satisfaction helps to identify service gaps which once addressed will improve the quality of services and hence utilization. Clients' satisfaction may be considered to be one of the desired outcomes of care. An expression of satisfaction or dissatisfaction is also the client's judgment on the quality of care in all its aspects, but particularly pertaining to the interpersonal process. However, it should be remembered that, unless special precautions are taken, clients may be reluctant to reveal their opinions for fear of alienating their attendants (40).

Exit point interviews with the pregnant women revealed that all clients were addressed or urged about having an HIV blood test and all of the pregnant women were counseled about HIV/AIDS.

One hundred seventy eight (91.3%) of the respondents from exit interview reported that adequate time was allocated for PMTCT counseling, whereas from observation of client-provider interaction it was found that the average time used for counseling and testing was 20 minutes and out of 6 pre-test counseling observations only on three and two session discussed about risk reduction and PMTCT, support service and importance of ANC respectively. According to the national guideline these show that there is problem about transferring of enough information to client which needs to be discussed during counseling which is stated points on the National guideline (Anex-6) to be discussed during pre-test counseling and post-test counseling (4). Missing to discuss about support services, antenatal care and its advantage and about PMTCT service may increase drop outs in the antenatal care and delivery services.

Majority (97%) of the pregnant women interviewed responded that they satisfied with the counseling. However, on observation of client counselor interaction on pre and post test counseling important points were not included (Anex-6) which is stated on the national guideline (4) even if all of the pregnant women interviewed have negative result which makes them and the counselors happy and satisfy. However, the transferring of most information to the client is not considered by the counselors. This might be due to lack of refresher training to the counselors and lack of external and internal supportive supervision of the counselors which is complained by all counselors during the interview.

Concerning clients' satisfaction with the services in this study, 92.2% felt comfortable with the counselors' client handling/respect; 91.5% were satisfied with technical competence of the counselors; and 91.9% of the clients believed that they had benefited from the counseling discussions. Generally, 89.8% of the clients reported being satisfied with the pretest and/or post testing counseling discussions which is similar to study done in Thailand (31).

Even though the overall quality of the counseling services in terms of content of the counseling, duration of the counseling and counselors' competence (interpersonal relationships, gathering and giving information) of the surveyed hospitals were more or less comparable to different studies done elsewhere, there still remains a lot to be improved to avert MTCT of HIV.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Both of the hospitals offered pre-test and post-test counseling, individually. Both of them had a separate room for counseling and mostly, the counseling and testing was performed on the same day they come without further appointments. The uptake of HCT and a return rate to collect their test results among the ANC client was very high. The hospitals had more than two trained PMTCT counselors; however, most of the counselors complained that they lacked refreshment training. Some of the site coordinators also shared this idea and urged training of additional counselors and refreshment courses for those who are on job to improve the service quality.

Overall, counselor's communicative skill (introductory/interpersonal relationship, gathering information from the clients, and giving information to the clients) was generally "satisfactory". The majority of pre-test sessions included the basic information on HIV transmission and prevention and PMTCT. However, this study revealed that the discussions were simple and lacking in depth and coverage in many of the counseling sessions. Many of the counselors were making push and failed to cover all the clients and topics. Moreover, the clients were not given chance to express their ideas to consent or to decline the blood testing.

All clients who had undergone HIV blood test had also undergone post-test individual counseling. However, even though the basic topics were covered, there were significant shortcomings in the comprehensiveness/depth of the information given, coverage of the clients, and in the time allotted for the counseling session.

Direct observation revealed that the basic topics were covered in most of the pre-and/or post-test sessions, and majority of those counseled comprehended the information; however, nearly a quarter of the clients didn't understand why they were offered HCT particularly during their pregnancy time. The vast majority (86.7%) of the clients stayed in the health centers up to 2:00 hours, which is regarded as acceptable waiting time to get the services they wanted. Most of the clients also indicated to have spent unreasonably long counseling sessions, however, the vast majority of the women interviewed were satisfied with the counseling and counselor interactions, and believed to have gained new things they didn't know.

Recommendations

Better management and supervision of the PMTCT program is needed by the administrative health bureau, with ongoing mentoring, performance evaluation and development of the skills of the counselors. This is likely to include, as a minimum, dedicated site coordinators, and specific plans for mentoring and maintaining counseling quality, and developing a check list for antenatal health education.

The counselors need to adhere to the guidelines of counseling and be committed and devote time to pre and post-test counseling sessions to equip the clients with the necessary and relevant information to make the women fully understand the prevention of HIV transmission and to enable them to use the interventions available to prevent mother-to-child transmission. The administrative health bureau should facilitate ongoing (refreshment) training for the counselors to equip them with recent information. As well additional health workers should be trained to share the burden of the work.

Acronyms

AIDS	; Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
ANC	; Antenatal Care
ART	; Anti retro-viral therapy
ARV	; Antiretroviral drug
BCC	; Behavior Change Communication
FHEW	; Female Health Extension worker
FP	; Family Planning
HAPCO	; HIV/AIDS Prevention and Control Office
HCT	; HIV counseling and testing
HF	; Health Facility
PMTCT	; Prevention of mother to child transmission

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Conflict of interest

There is no any conflicts of interest between authors.

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